

DAMAGE BEHAVIOR IN ANGLE PLY CFRP LAMINATES WITH DIFFERENT PLY THICKNESS

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ABSTRACT

Nowadays, CFRP is being widely used especially in aircraft industry in regards to its strength and light-weighted properties. A unidirectional CFRP laminates has high stiffness and strength in its fiber direction but low stiffness and strength in off-axis direction. Thus this study tries to understand the factors affecting damage behavior in angle-ply laminates. There are already many studies investigating the damage behavior of cross-ply laminates. This study investigates the mechanical properties and damage behavior of angle-ply CFRP laminates with different thickness by manipulating the number of ply. The laminates tested here have fiber orientation of $[0/\theta_n]_s$. Tensile loads are loaded and unloaded and Young's modulus reduction is calculated before and after cracks formation. After unloaded, cracks formations throughout test specimens are observed by using X-ray images. Crack density is calculated by calculating the number of cracks that penetrated a 30 mm strain gauge, adhered in loading direction. The relationship between Young's modulus reduction and crack density between every laminates with different ply thickness are observed and compared.

1 INTRODUCTION

In the past few years, Boeing introduced B787 with 50% of its body structure is made up of carbon fibre reinforced plastics (CFRP). In regards to CFRP's light-weighted yet strong properties, the fuel efficiency of the aircraft increased by 20%. Furthermore, CFRP can be moulded in large size or small size, thus reducing the number of components such as bolts, nuts and etc. These kinds of properties give a new hope to industries that require speed and strength combined especially in aerospace and automotive industry.

CFRP has directional strength properties which means the properties such as stiffness, strength and etc. are depending on the layouts. Unidirectional fiber composites have high stiffness and strength in the fiber direction but low stiffness and strength in off-axis direction. This also means that it can be designed so that its properties can be manipulated efficiently. Angle-ply and cross ply laminates are among the simplest form of laminates that can be formed. Angle-ply laminates are laminates that contain off-axis angle plies such as 45°, 60°, 75° and etc. Meanwhile, cross-ply laminates are laminates that consists of 0° and 90° plies. In reality, laminates with more complex stacking sequences are being used in aeroplanes and so on.

There are already a lot of studies (experimental data and analysis) on stiffness reduction for cross-ply laminates [0/90]. Fukunaga et al. [1] had investigated the stress distribution in a cracked cross-ply laminate by using shear lag model, and by taking consideration of thermal residual stresses and Poisson effect. Furthermore, Hashin [2] had evaluated the stress distribution in a cracked cross-ply laminate using a 2 dimensional stress analysis. Both of these analyses have good agreement with experimental results. On the other hand, Vinogradov et al. [3] analysed the stiffness reduction of angle-ply laminates containing intralaminar cracks in the middle laminae.

Therefore, the objective of this study is to investigate the mechanical properties and damage behavior of angle-ply laminates with different thickness by manipulating the number of ply.

2 METHODS AND MATERIALS

2.1. Materials and specimens

Table 1 shows the laminates that were formed by using an autoclave machine with temperature of 130°C and pressure of 0.2 MPa. There are two type of materials used which are carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) prepreg and glass fiber reinforced plastics (GFRP) prepreg.

The laminates are cut by using a composite material cutting machine (AC-300CF, Maruto). The specimens' measurement is as in figure 1. GFRP tabs with measurement of 50mm x 25 mm are glued to the specimens' ends by using adhesive glue (Araldite, Huntsman Japan) to provide better grip when loads are applied. Figure 1 (a) shows the 2-axis strain gauge (KFG-2-120-D16, Kyowa) used in monotonic tensile test while figure 1 (b) shows the 30 mm 1-axis strain gauge (KFG-5-120-D16, Kyowa) used in loading-unloading tensile test.

CFRP prepreg (T700SC/2500, Torayca) 0.05 mm per ply		GFRP prepreg (GE352G135SB, Mitsubishi Rayon) 0.1 mm per ply	
Stacking sequences	Approximate thickness (mm)	Stacking sequences	Approximate thickness (mm)
$[0_3/45_{12}]_S$	1.60	$[0/90]_6$	1.40
$[0_3/75_{12}]_S$		$[0/90]_8$	1.80
$[0_3/90_{12}]_S$		$[0/45]_8$	
$[0_3/45_{18}]_S$	2.10	$[0/45]_9$	2.00
$[0_3/75_{18}]_S$		$[0_3/90_{12}]_S$	3.00
$[0_3/90_{18}]_S$			

Table 1 Stacking sequences and approximate thickness of laminates

Fig. 1 Specimen configuration and the different type of strain gauge used for (a) monotonic tensile test and (b) loading unloading tensile test

2.2. Tensile test

With cross head speed of 1mm/min, two types of tensile test were done. There are monotonic tensile test and loading-unloading tensile test. The experiments were done by using tensile test machine (Tensilon RTF-1350, A&D).

2.2.1. Monotonic tensile test

Monotonic tensile tests were done in order to obtain the mechanical properties of each laminates tested. Loads were applied until fracture. Two-axis strain gauges are glued on the specimens to obtain the longitudinal and transverse strain.

2.2.2. Loading unloading tensile test

Loading unloading tensile tests were done to investigate the stiffness reduction and damage behavior of every specimen. For this purpose, a 3 cm strain gauge is glued on the specimen surface in loading direction, while two 5mm strain gauges are glued on the other surface in transverse direction. After the specimens are unloaded, the cracks formed were observed.

2.2.3. Crack observation

Figure 2 shows the examples of crack observation methods for CFRP and GFRP laminates.

Cracks observation for CFRP and GFRP were different because of the different properties of these two types of laminates. As CFRP laminates are opaque, X-ray light (Soft X-Ray Radiography Machine M-100S, SOFTEX) is exposed to the laminates for 3 minutes. The X-ray films are then processed in a darkroom by using developer solution, stop solution, fixer solution, and distilled water for 4 minutes, 1 minute, 3 minutes and 5 minutes respectively.

Meanwhile, as GFRP laminates are half-transparent, videos were recorded during loading unloading experiments.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 2 Examples of cracks observation methods for (a) CFRP 90 degree 36 plies and (b) GFRP 90 degree 16 plies

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Mechanical properties

3.1.2 Carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) laminates

Figure 3 shows the stress- strain curve for CFRP laminates with off-axis angle of 45 degree, 75 degree and 90 degree. From this test, we understand that as the number of off-axis plies increased, the strength decreased. As the off-axis angles are inclined towards 90 degree, the longitudinal strain became more slanted towards 2.0%. Cracks are assumed to be formed at some point where there is no increased in stress of the laminates. The cracks are assumed to be formed earlier in 45 degree off-axis laminates than in 90 degree off axis laminates.

Table 2 shows the mechanical properties (Young's modulus, maximum tensile stress, fracture longitudinal strain and Poisson's ratio) for every CFRP laminates tested.

Fig. 3 Stress-strain relationship for CFRP laminates with off-axis angle of (a) 45 degree (b) 75 degree and (c) 90 degree

CFRP	Young`s Modulus [GPa]	Maximum Tensile Stress [MPa]	Fracture Longitudinal Strain [%]	Poisson`s ratio
$[0_3/45_{18}]_S$	25.5	368	1.71	0.392
$[0_3/45_{12}]_S$	32.0	538	1.83	0.344
$[0_3/75_{18}]_S$	23.7	367	1.94	0.086
$[0_3/75_{12}]_S$	32.9	503	1.74	0.091
$[0_3/90_{18}]_S$	24.2	306	1.60	0.057
$[0_3/90_{12}]_S$	30.4	523	1.96	0.031

Table 2 Mechanical properties of CFRP laminates

3.1.3 Glass fiber reinforced plastics (GFRP) laminates

Figure 4 shows the stress and strain relationship for GFRP laminates with off-axis angle of 45 and 90 degree. Table 2 shows the mechanical properties (Young`s modulus, maximum tensile stress, fracture longitudinal strain and Poisson`s ratio) for every GFRP laminates tested.

Even though the number of plies for off-axis angle is increased, there are almost no changes in the stress-strain curve for the laminates. As load is applied to laminates with off-axis angle of 90 degree, strain increased until 1.5% before it was fractured. It was fractured mainly because of delamination between 0° and 90° plies. On the other hand, for laminates with off-axis angle of 45 degree, as load was applied it remains linear until strain of about 2% until it were fractured at strain of 2.4%. Based on observation of the cracked specimens, there are no cracks that can be observed except at the fractured point.

Fig. 4 Stress-strain relationship for GFRP laminates with off-axis angle of (a) 45 degree and (b) 90 degree

GFRP	Young`s Modulus [GPa]	Maximum Tensile Stress [MPa]	Fracture Longitudinal Strain [%]	Poisson`s ratio
$[0_3/90_{12}]_s$	16.8	211	2.61	0.104
$[0/90_9]_s$	14.5	113	0.94	0.097
$[0/90_6]_s$	15.1	145	1.66	0.091
$[0/45_8]_s$	13.2	190	2.46	0.419
$[0/45_9]_s$	13.0	178	2.35	0.457

Table 3 Mechanical properties of GFRP laminates

3.2. Stiffness reduction

Figure 4 (a), (b) and (c) shows the stiffness reduction and crack density relationship for CFRP laminates with off-axis angle of 45 degree, 75 degree and 90 degree respectively. From these figures, it can be concluded that as the number of plies of off-axis angle increases, the stiffness reduction increases. The amount of stiffness reduction differed based on the off-axis angle and number of plies.

In figure 4 (a), for 45 degree laminates with 24 plies and 36 plies, the stiffness are reduced to about 0.88 when the crack densities are about 0.64 [cr/cm] and 1.32 [cr/cm]. Although the number of plies increased, there are only small differences in the stiffness reduction for laminates with off-axis angle of 45 degree. Meanwhile, in figure 4 (b), for 75 degree laminates with 24 plies and 36 plies, the stiffness is reduced to about 0.85 and 0.75 respectively. The same goes to 90 degree laminates in figure 4 (c).

As cracks formed in 45 degree laminates, the 45 degree plies still carries some of the load applied, thus, resulting in the small differences of stiffness reduction. On the other hand, as cracks formed in 90 degree laminates, the 90 degree plies did not carry any load, leaving only the 0 degree plies to carry the load. As the number of plies increased from 24 plies to 26 plies, the ratio of load to be carried by the 0 degree plies increased.

On the other hand, figure 5 shows the stiffness reduction and crack density relationship for GFRP laminates with off-axis angle of 90 degree. Even though the thicknesses are different for every laminates, but the stiffness reduction gradient are almost the same except stiffness in $[0_3/90_{12}]_s$ laminates is reduced until about 0.6 before fractured.

(a)

(b)

(c)
Fig. 5 Stiffness reduction-crack density relationship for CFRP laminates with off-axis angle of (a) 45 degree (b) 75 degree and (c) 90 degree

Fig. 6 Stiffness reduction-crack density relationship for GFRP laminates with off-axis angle of 90 degree

9 CONCLUSIONS

As a conclusion, the mechanical properties and damage behavior of angle-ply laminates with different thickness has been investigated. As the middle laminae is thickened, the stiffness reduction increased. The stiffness reduction and crack density behaviour for CFRP laminates and GFRP laminates are different because of the properties of the materials itself.

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